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Validation of performance of Joint Excitation and Reactive Power Controllers using commercially available power system analysis software packages

ABSTRACT

This paper presents the comparative analysis of two different approaches of reactive power allocation among synchronous generators within a steam power plant (SPP). The analysis is performed in order to validate by comparison of simulation results obtained with two most widely used power system analysis software packages, PSSE®PTI Siemens and DIgSILENT Power Factory, with the case study measurement results. The measurements are obtained at the point of common coupling (PCC) of two adjacent Steam Power Plants (SPP) following the action of Joint Excitation and Reactive Power Controllers (JEQC). The accuracy of simulation results is essential for the Transmission System Operator (TSO) who is using these software packages to calculate power losses in the network due to reactive power flows. The allocation of reactive power (Q) among the generators involved is performed by JEQC according to criterion of maximum Q reserve at plants PCC, while the algorithms built in PSSE®PTI Siemens and DIgSILENT Power Factory calculate Q allocation in order to minimize transmission losses by activating the OPF option. The aim of JEQC testing initiated by the Transmission System Operator (TSO), was to check the compatibility of results obtained by the JEQC algorithm action and that obtained by optimal power flow algorithm based on minimization of transmission losses criterion. The compatibility of the results, if confirmed, should enable the use of JEQC as an efficient tool for secondary voltage control in the power system.

The analysis was performed for case study of parallel operation of two excitation and reactive power controllers (JEQC) installed in two largest steam power plants in Serbia, SPP "Nikola Tesla A" and SPP "Nikola Tesla B", which are electrically close to each other. The main purpose of the JEQC is to perform a slow voltage control at PCC of the plants by automatically adjusting the levels of generated reactive power of the SPP's generators while i) ensuring the uniform and synchronized response of all participating generators in case of power system disturbances, ii) preventing generators from operating in forbidden areas of the capability chart where overheating of stator core can occur, iii) restoring operating point of the generator after a major disturbance to the pre-fault value. The case study considered the Q - V controller outputs at the high voltage side of the SPP's step-up transformer. The parameters used are given in the official technical documentation provided by the owner of the SPP. This was done due to high voltage side location of the measuring points in the transmission network which TSO uses for gathering relevant data for safe and reliable operation of the transmission system. The performed simulations confirmed that all calculations results are in compliance with the national Grid Code (official version released on June 2014).

1 INTRODUCTION

The consequence of the market deregulation process is a tendency of TSO to manage the power transmission system with the primary criteria to maximize profit or to minimize the transfer of reactive power

(Q), thus leaving enough space for the transfer of active power (P), as well as the minimization of transmission losses in the power system due to the mandatory purchase of losses by the TSO. At the same time the criteria determining the quality of electricity supply should be satisfied [1], [2], [3]. In the background

there are technical conditions such as the maintaining maximal reactive power margins to the collapse point of the system as well as keeping the appropriate distribution of reactive power between generators in power plants. 10 years ago, after the partial collapse of the Serbian power system, TSO has requested that SPP TENT A at all times ensures equal reactive reserve on all generators in the plant. On that occasion, it was noted that during a disturbance one of the plant generators reached the rotor current limit, long before others did, which further aggravated the functioning of the observed system that was already tense. The electric power system of Serbia at the time was characterized by a low voltage conditions and generators operated deeply into the inductive parts of their capability curves. The generators often were required to decrease the active power in order to enable enough reactive power for voltages in the power system to be kept within the prescribed range. In SPP TENT A a newly developed device JEQC was installed a few years ago which ensured at all times, maximum Q reserve uniformly distributed between generators, according to the current operating state of the generator and other equipment. Provision of the required amount of reactive power reserve from power plants in the power system as well as the distribution of reactive power between generators in power plants is carried out using the algorithm based on (1),(2),[4],[5],[6],[7].

The reactive power reserve of the power plant was calculated using (1)

$$k_{plant} = \frac{Q_{request}}{Q_{max_plant} - Q_{min_plant}} \quad (1)$$

and the reactive power reserve of each generator using (2)

$$k_{igen} = \frac{Q_i - Q_{imax}}{Q_{imax} - Q_{imin}} \quad (2)$$

With the development of Serbian transmission system and development of adjacent national transmission systems, the voltage conditions have changed and now the power system is characterized by high overnight voltages at important nodes. The situation regarding generators has become critical because they are now forced to operate the most of the day in a capacitive area of capability curve. These operating regimes are characterized with the occurrence of the problems related to the temperature rise in the generator stator core. Temperature problems are of a local nature and they lead to uneven distribution and increased density of the magnetic fields in end core area due to operation of generators in the capacitive area. Temperature monitoring devices which are placed in stator core area give a general picture of the stator temperature distribution. Critical hot spots temperature in this zone can be much higher than the measured temperature of the core and can lead to serious degradation of stator

winding insulation in a relatively short period of time [8]. The owners of SPP also reported the uneven heating of the generators that occurs when maintaining maximum reactive reserves. It should be noted that the JEQC maintains the same distance from the capacitive limits on all generators in the power plant and such favourably affects the heating of the stator and in results the rotor and the stator windings being more heated when generator is operating in inductive area of capability chart. The possibility of obtaining the maximum Q reserves at the PCC should be specified through Grid Code and adequately compensated to plant owners. It is also important to note that the synchronous generators are the only source of dynamic reactive power in the Serbian power system and that reactive power should be available for compensation during transients. There are the opposing requirements with respect to managing the transmission system operation related to minimisation of the losses at one hand and the stability of power system on the other. Furthermore, the uniform heating of the generators involves the loading of generators proportionally to their nominal apparent power (3) and, on the other hand, it is necessary to respect the criteria of maintaining optimal voltage and reactive reserve at all times.

$$k_{igen} = \frac{\sqrt{P^2 + Q^2}}{S_{ni}} \quad (3)$$

Due to implementation of a large number of renewable energy sources in the electricity systems the ENTSO-E defined requirements for the plant as a whole, as opposed to defining requirements for each generator. In this sense, a JEQC observes power plant as a virtual generation unit, in terms of voltage and reactive power, with a single Q-V characteristic. TSO manages the bus voltage where the facility is connected and defines ranges of voltage values for a given generation level of reactive power. The JEQC device, when implemented manages the Q-V characteristic. In this way, TSO may perform minimization of losses in the transmission system by controlling voltages at the connection points of the power plants, in case that the power plant is equipped with JEQC device. At the same time JEQC provides the maximum reactive power reserve that power plant can provide to the system, in order to prevent the occurrence of voltage collapse [10],[11],[12].

For daily operation of the power system it is necessary to verify whether the optimal distribution of reactive power between generators, in order to maintain the maximum Q reserve, is in contradiction with the results obtained conducting optimal power flow simulations. The most recent versions of software packages offer the possibility to calculate optimal power flow using as a criteria the maximum reserve of reactive power and the minimum transmission losses at the same time [13],[14]. Problem and the importance of the optimal power flow calculations is in the ex-

pansion and in the most recent version of the software package PowerFactory 2016 [15] it is one of the items that have been improved since the release of previous version. Below is an excerpt from the PowerFactory 2016 software package Release Notes [15]: "Optimal Power Flow includes a new feature that aims to ensure the maximum reactive power reserve. There are three options for achieving this goal. First option is minimum deviation from the target value of reactive power: target value is defined per generator, the option determines setpoint values per generator which reaches the slightest deviation from the values defined by the needed reactive power reserves. Second option is the least deviation from the minimum value of reactive power reserve: setpoints are defined so that the deviation from the lower limit value of the reactive power reserve that should be provided is minimum. Third option is the least deviation from the maximum value of reactive power reserve: setpoints are defined so that deviations from the upper limits of reactive power reserves that should be provided are as minimal as possible. New functions implemented in 2016 PowerFactory for selective minimization of the transmission losses offers the possibility of minimizing losses only for certain parts of the network, for example, for a given zone, area etc. When this function is selected the losses of all elements within the defined part of the network is reduced to a minimum."

Two largest steam power plants in the Republic of

Serbia have the JEQC device implemented. In order to optimize the operation of the system TSO's objective was to compare the results and further consider the possibility of combining the two criteria mentioned above at different levels of operational management of the transmission system. The aim is to ensure benefit for all participants in the transmission system, both companies and customers, so that they pay the lowest price for delivered electricity. For conducting case study calculations and simulations two software packages were used, PowerFactory version 15.2 and PSSE@PTISiemens [16]. The most recent version of the software package DIgSILENT PowerFactory became available for customers at the end of February 2016.

2 THE SIMULATION OF SPP'S "TENT A" AND "TENT B" WITH DATA RECORDED ON 30TH OF JANUARY 2014.

The value of active power, reactive power and voltage that are recorded on 30th of January 2014 at 7:30 am are considered as initial values. These values and other corresponding parameters are shown in the table below. The initial bus voltages were: $V_{220}=227.9$ kV and $V_{400}=404$ kV. The simulation results using DIgSILENT and PSSE are shown in Figures 1 a), 1 b), 2 a) and 2 b), where the coefficients k_Q represent the dependence between generated reactive power

Table 1.- Initial state in SPP TENT A, initial outputs for given hours (07:30) of the day 30.01.2014.

	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	B1	B2
P [MW]	199	184	303	303	346	314	-	-
Q [MVar]	61.5	49	40	55.5	64.5	50	-	-
Vg [kV]	0.99715	0.992	0.98507	0.99065	1.02184	1.01095	-	-

Figure 1a).- Reactive power responses for 30 01 2014. JEQC is turned off, old coefficients of voltage reactive drop of regulation are set, the equivalent Thevenin EMS of the 220 kV network changes in steps 213 kV - 200 kV - 190 kV

Figure 1b) - Reactive power responses and generator load coefficients k_Q for 30_01_2014 at SPP TENT A. JEQC is turned off

Figure 2a) - Reactive power responses for 31_12_2014 when JEQC is turned on ($V_{220ref} = 227,4 \text{ kV}$, $V_{400ref} = 402,8 \text{ kV}$, $s = 0,03$ at SPP TENT A buses), new coefficients of voltage reactive drop of regulation are set, The equivalent network Thevenin EMF of the 400 kV network changes in three steps: 400 kV-390 kV-370 kV

Figure 2b) - Reactive power responses and generator load coefficients k_Q in SPP TENT A and TENT B for 31_12_2014, JEQC is turned on

and available reserve of the generator in the respective operating point.

From Fig. 2a) and 2b) it is obvious that the JEQC is capable to maintain the maximum reactive reserve under changing load conditions.

3 THE SOFTWARE DERIVED MODELS

The power system snapshot's were created in two steps for characteristic hours: the forecast models were made day ahead and then recorded load at hours of

interest was implemented in the models. In this way a realistic picture of the system (snapshot) at 03:30, 10:30 and 19:30 was created. These three characteristic hours are: the morning minimum model, the morning maximum model and the evening maximum model of Serbian power system.

Models of the system which are given in .uct form are compared with data recorded by the owner of SPP (JP EPS) for the dates above in characteristic hours obtained by the Institute "Nikola Tesla" (IENT). It was necessary to adjust values provided by the Institute by subtracting the value which represents auxiliary consumption of each generating unit in power plants of interest and then to take into account the losses that occur in the step-up transformer. Using this procedure the commitment of units was calculated at the high voltage side of step-up transformers. This was done due to the measuring points locations in the transmission network which TSO uses for gathering relevant plant operational data. Deviations that have occurred are mainly due to measurements with different time stamps. The calculations results show a good matching between the recorded value on high voltage

busbars and simulated response. Therefore, the model was validated and it was decided that it is good enough to carry out the further analysis.

The calculated data are shown in Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4. The active and reactive power sign is negative for generated power and positive for absorbed power in aforementioned Tables.

4 COMPARISON AND EVALUATION OF THE RESULTS

After the first round of simulations the second step of the proposed analysis included running the OPF calculations with certain options activated for purpose of simulating situations with JEQC turned on [15]. Limitations that must be considered during the optimal power flow calculations are:

- the generator's maximum and minimum power limits,
- the voltage limits,
- the reactive power injection limits
- the overhead lines and transformer's power transmission limits

Table 2.- Calculated data for SPP TENT A, simulation outputs for given specific hours of the day (03:30), models are created for these hours in order to conduct daily analysis

Unit	Bus type	Voltage [kV]	Active Power P[MW]	Reactive Power Q [MVar]
TENT A4	2	226.02	-241.3	-12.3
TENT A3	2	226.02	0	0
TENT A2	2	226.02	-187.9	-16.5
TENT A1	2	226.02	-156.2	-9.5
TENT A5	2	403.321	-319.6	-17.8
TENT A6	2	403.321	-319.4	-13.5

Table 3.- Calculated data for SPP TENT A, simulation outputs for given specific hours of the day (10:30), models are created for these hours in order to conduct daily analysis

Unit	Bus type	Voltage[kV]	ActivePower P[MW]	Reactive Power Q [MVar]
TENT A4	2	227.15	-286.1	-105.4
TENT A3	2	227.15	0	0
TENT A2	2	227.15	-179.7	-85.5
TENT A1	2	227.15	-190.4	-82.5
TENT A5	2	404.5406	-308	-51.1
TENT A6	2	404.5406	-343.1	-53.5

Table 4.- Calculated data for SPP TENT A, simulation outputs for given specific hours of the day (19:30), models are created for these hours in order to conduct daily analysis

Unit	Bus type	Voltage[kV]	Active Power P[MW]	Reactive Power Q [MVar]
TENT A4	2	224.98	-293.6	-129.4
TENT A3	2	224.98	0	0
TENT A2	2	224.98	-182.7	-83.4
TENT A1	2	224.98	-196.1	-89.2
TENT A5	2	402.3029	-330.8	-72.2
TENT A6	2	402.3029	-320.7	-78.3

The comparison between measured and calculated data is shown in *Table 5*, *Table 6* and *Table 7*. The active and reactive power sign is negative for generated power and positive for absorbed power in aforementioned Tables. An acceptable agreement is demonstrated between measured and calculated data.

Table 5.- Recorded (first 3 columns) and calculated data for SPP TENT A, (last 3 columns) for given specific hours (03:30) of the day using OPF option

Unit	Voltage [kV]	Active Power P[MW]	Reactive Power Q [MVar]	Voltage [kV]	Active Power P[MW]	Reactive Power Q [MVar]
TENT A4	226.02	-241.3	-12.3	226	-255	10.1271
TENT A3	226.02	0	0	226	0	0
TENT A2	226.02	-187.9	-16.5	226	-158	-13.4771
TENT A1	226.02	-156.2	-9.5	226	-158	-3.47281
TENT A5	403.321	-319.6	-17.8	403	-300	-14
TENT A6	403.321	-319.4	-13.5	403	-300	-14

Table 6.- Recorded (first 3 columns) and calculated data for SPP TENT A, (last 3 columns) for given specific hours (10:30) of the day using OPF option

Unit	Voltage [kV]	Active Power P[MW]	Reactive Power Q [MVar]	Voltage [kV]	Active Power P[MW]	Reactive Power Q [MVar]
TENT A4	227.15	-286.1	-105.4	227	-286	-86.35
TENT A3	227.15	0	0	227	0	0
TENT A2	227.15	-179.7	-85.5	227	-167	-54.442
TENT A1	227.15	-190.4	-82.5	227	-168	-54.268
TENT A5	404.5406	-308	-51.1	404	-278	-140
TENT A6	404.5406	-343.1	-53.5	404	-314	-140

Table 7.- Recorded (first 3 columns) and calculated data for SPP TENT A, (last 3 columns) simulation outputs for given specific hours (19:30) of the day using OPF option

Unit	Voltage [kV]	Active Power P[MW]	Reactive Power Q [MVar]	Voltage [kV]	Active Power P[MW]	Reactive Power Q [MVar]
TENT A4	224.98	-293.6	-129.4	224	-298	-97.573
TENT A3	224.98	0	0	224	0	-97.575
TENT A2	224.98	-182.7	-83.4	224	-177	-59.871
TENT A1	224.98	-196.1	-89.2	224	-178	-59.698
TENT A5	402.3029	-330.8	-72.2	402	-313	-87
TENT A6	402.3029	-320.7	-78.3	402	-304	-104

5 CONCLUSIONS

The analysis carried out by comparing the values obtained with OPF simulations and values obtained with conventional Power Flow simulations led to the following conclusions:

- the voltages vary in range of values in accordance with the Grid Code on a daily basis;
- by applying JEQC automation, where possible in order to manage voltage values and reactive power, it is possible to get the expansion of system operational limits, as well as the improvement of the voltage quality and the supply security;
- by implementation of the OPF principle it is possible to reduce the total losses in the transmission system, and that is shown through simulations and comparison with conventional PF simulations.

Based on the analysis carried out and the output parameters obtained by OPF calculation the main conclusion drawn is that the JEQC has a positive effect on the transmission system operation by reducing the losses in the transmission system while not interfering with the optimization process which insures system operation in accordance with national Grid Code.

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